

LATTICE BOLTZMANN SIMULATION OF NON-DARCY FLOW

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ABSTRACT. Darcy’s law is widely recognized as being inapplicable for modeling porous media systems in which the Reynolds number (Re) is large. However, many open questions regarding non-Darcy flow exist, including the effect of pore morphology and topology on the onset of non-Darcy behavior. We use a multiple-relaxation-time lattice Boltzmann method to simulate single-phase flow through two ideal systems consisting of stable, non-overlapping sphere packs generated using a truncated log-normal distribution of sphere sizes and constrained to yield a range of realistic porosities. We examine these simulations at the microscale to determine changes in the flow field as a function of the Re. We interpret these results using the Forchheimer equation, and comment on the suitability of this expression and a potential extension to this common empirical form.

1. INTRODUCTION

At the macroscale, single-phase flow in porous media at very low flow rates is described by Darcy’s law, written for flow in isotropic media as:

$$-\nabla p + \rho g = \frac{\mu}{\kappa} u_d, \tag{1}$$

where p is the fluid pressure, ρ is the fluid density, g is the gravitational acceleration, μ is the fluid viscosity, u_d is the Darcy velocity, and κ is the intrinsic permeability of the medium. It is widely recognized that Darcy’s law loses its validity if Reynolds number (Re) exceeds a critical value Re_0 that depends upon the pore morphology and topology of the medium and the characteristics of scales used to define Re. Determined from experiments or numerical simulations, values of the critical Re are generally believed to satisfy $0.1 \leq Re_0 \leq 10$ when based on the Darcy velocity and averaged grain diameter [19]. The onset of non-Darcy flow in single-fluid phase porous medium systems is most likely to occur in the vicinity of high-capacity wells, especially in coarse grained material or fractured systems.

As Re increases, there is a transition zone from a Darcy flow regime to a regime in which inertial effects become important, which we will refer to as the inertial or non-Darcy regime. An empirical extension of Darcy’s law known as the Forchheimer equation was proposed more than a century ago [6], and a similar form was also suggested by Ergun [4] to account for the onset of the nonlinearity:

$$-\nabla p + \rho g = \frac{\mu}{\kappa_f} u_d + \beta \rho u_d^2, \tag{2}$$

where κ_f is the Forchheimer permeability and β is an inertial coefficient. Rearranging Eq. (2) into a dimensionless form and substituting $\text{Re} = \rho u_d \bar{D}_2 / \mu$ yields:

$$\frac{(-\nabla p + \rho g) \bar{D}_2^2}{\mu u_d} = \frac{\bar{D}_2^2}{\kappa_f} + \beta \text{Re} \bar{D}_2, \quad (3)$$

where $\bar{D}_2 = \int D^3 N(D) dD / \int D^2 N(D) dD$ is the surface averaged grain diameter and $N(D)$ is the distribution function of the grain diameter D . Eq. (3) indicates that the pressure drop is accounted for as a sum of viscous and inertial terms. Therefore, the Forchheimer equation can be used to describe both the Darcy and non-Darcy regimes, and the transition between them.

As alternatives to the Forchheimer equation, several studies have also suggested a cubic law to describe the transition between Darcy and non-Darcy flow [5, 15]. In these approaches, the inertial coefficient β is not constant but is linearly related to the velocity. However, by comparing numerical simulations of flow through a two-dimensional and a three-dimensional periodic flow cell, Fourar *et al.* [7] showed that the Forchheimer quadratic relation accurately represents flow through three-dimensional porous medium systems; and the cubic relation is in accord with simulation data for flow through two-dimensional porous medium systems where the transition zone between the Darcy and non-Darcy regimes occurs over a wider range of Re .

The physical reasons for the onset of the non-Darcy regime and the accuracy of the Forchheimer equation have been investigated using experimental [3, 18], theoretical [13, 15], and numerical means at the microscale [7, 20, 21]. However, few studies have been devoted to examining microscale flow patterns through realistic three-dimensional porous medium systems and quantitatively investigating the effect of pore morphology and topology on the onset of non-Darcy behavior.

The objectives of this work are: (1) to examine the effects of pore morphology and topology on the onset of non-Darcy flow, (2) to observe the microscale flow patterns that evolve in a realistic porous medium with increasing Re , and (3) to evaluate the ability of the Forchheimer equation to describe, on a macroscopic level, simulations performed at the microscale.

2. MULTIPLE-RELAXATION-TIME (MRT) LATTICE BOLTZMANN MODEL

We used the lattice-Boltzmann (LB) approach to solve for the microscale flow field in porous medium systems over a range of Re . The LB method is a numerical scheme developed recently to simulate fluid dynamics [1, 14]. It involves approximating the microscopic Boltzmann equation, which can be viewed as a discrete approximation of the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations based on kinetic theory [9]. In the LB method, fluid flow is represented by the distribution functions of fluid particles moving on a regular lattice. The so-called D3Q19 lattice was used for this work, where ‘‘D3’’ indicates three dimensions, and ‘‘Q19’’ indicates a 19-dimensional space with corresponding velocity vectors \mathbf{e}_i ($i = 0, 1, \dots, 18$). The evolution of the fluid particle distributions is governed by the discrete Boltzmann equation [2]:

$$\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{e}, t + 1) - \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \mathbf{S} \left[\mathbf{f}^{(\text{eq})}(\mathbf{x}, t) - \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}, t) \right] + \mathbf{F}, \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{f} and \mathbf{F} denote Q -dimensional column vectors:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}, t) &= [f_0(\mathbf{x}, t), f_1(\mathbf{x}, t), \dots, f_{18}(\mathbf{x}, t)]^\top, \\ \mathbf{F} &= (F_0, F_1, \dots, F_{18})^\top,\end{aligned}\tag{5}$$

where \mathbf{f} is a vector of the distribution functions at lattice location \mathbf{x} and time t , and \mathbf{F} is the external forcing vector. Superscript \top denotes the transpose operator. The left side of Eq. (4) represents advection and indicates that the fluid particles $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ simply propagate in space according to the discrete velocity \mathbf{e} . The first term of the right side of Eq. (4) is the collision term and is approximated by a multiple-relaxation-time function of the particle distribution functions towards their equilibria $\mathbf{f}^{(eq)}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ via a $Q \times Q$ full collision matrix \mathbf{S} .

LB models with the MRT collision operators have been shown to yield a more accurate velocity field than the conventional LB models with so-called BGK, single-relaxation time collision operators [12, 17]. One can consider the MRT collision process in moment space instead of the discrete velocity space. Given a set of discrete velocity vectors \mathbf{e} and corresponding distribution functions $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}, t)$, a vector of moments $\mathbf{m}_i (i = 0, 1, \dots, 18)$ can be constructed by a projection of the distributions \mathbf{f} through a linear transformation, i.e.:

$$\mathbf{m} = \mathbf{M} \mathbf{f}; \quad \mathbf{f} = \mathbf{M}^{-1} \mathbf{m},$$

where \mathbf{M} is an integer transformation tensor, constructed via the Gram-Schmidt orthogonalization procedure [2, 10, 11]. The moments are related to the conserved (hydrodynamic) and unconserved (kinetic) physical properties, including the density, the momentum, the kinetic energy, the energy flux, and the viscous stress tensor. Hence, Eq. (4) can be written as:

$$\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{e}, t + 1) - \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \mathbf{M}^{-1} \widehat{\mathbf{S}} [\mathbf{m}^{(eq)}(\mathbf{x}, t) - \mathbf{m}(\mathbf{x}, t)].\tag{6}$$

The corresponding collision matrix $\widehat{\mathbf{S}} = \mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{M}^{-1}$ in the moment space is a diagonal matrix:

$$\widehat{\mathbf{S}} = \text{diag}(0, s_1, s_2, 0, s_3, 0, s_3, 0, s_3, s_4, s_5, s_4, s_5, s_6, s_6, s_6, s_7, s_7, s_7)\tag{7}$$

where s_i are the collision, or relaxation, parameters, indicating that the collision process for each moment m_i is accomplished by a linear relaxation towards its equilibrium $m_i^{(eq)}$. The transformation tensor \mathbf{M} and the functional forms of the equilibrium moments $\mathbf{m}^{(eq)}$ for the D3Q19 lattice are given in [2, 10].

The values of the collision parameters s_i that correspond to the conserved moments are irrelevant because $m^{(eq)}(\mathbf{x}, t) = m(\mathbf{x}, t)$ for the conserved moments; they have been set to zero in Eq. (7). In addition, symmetry on the chosen lattice is preserved by requiring some of the non-zero values of the elements of $\widehat{\mathbf{S}}$ to be equal. The kinematic viscosity ν is defined as:

$$\nu = \frac{1}{3} \left(\tau - \frac{1}{2} \right)\tag{8}$$

where τ is the single relaxation time. The collision parameters used in this work are specified following Ginzburg and d'Humières [8] to minimize the dependence of permeability on viscosity as:

$$s_1 = s_2 = s_4 = s_5 = s_6 = 1/\tau, \quad s_3 = s_7 = 8(2\tau - 1)/(8\tau - 1)\tag{9}$$

FIGURE 1. Portions of RSP1 (a) and RSP23 (b) pore geometries used in the simulations. Colored areas are solid spaces.

Note that the conventional BGK single-relaxation-time model is a special case of the generalized LB-MRT model, where the collision matrix is $\mathbf{S} = (1/\tau) \mathbf{I}$ and \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix.

The second term of the right-hand side of Eq. (4) accounts for the external forcing, of which the components are:

$$F_i = 3w_i\rho\mathbf{e}_i \cdot \mathbf{a}, \quad (10)$$

where $\rho = \sum_i f_i$ is the fluid density, \mathbf{a} is the acceleration due to external forces, and the weight coefficients for the D3Q19 model are usually chosen as $w_0 = 1/3$, $w_i = 1/18$ for $i = 1 - 6$, and $w_i = 1/36$ for $i = 7 - 18$. By imposing a constant driving force along the flow direction and varying the magnitude of this force and the viscosity, we obtained flow fields at varying Re.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

We simulated flow through two stable, non-overlapping random sphere packings, designated RSP1 and RSP23, respectively, using the pack algorithm developed in [22]. The sphere packings had log-normal grain-size distributions, for which $\bar{D}_2 = \bar{D}[1 + (\sigma/\bar{D})^2]$. RSP1 represents a uniform packing, with the relative standard deviation of the grain size $\tilde{\sigma} = \sigma/\bar{D} = 0.005$, while RSP23 represents a non-uniform packing with $\tilde{\sigma} = 0.65$. The average grain diameter \bar{D} of RSP1 and RSP23 was 0.2 mm, and the porosity ϕ was 0.45 and 0.33, respectively. To achieve reliable packings, both packings were simulated with at least 10,000 spheres. Because of the computational limitations, only portions of the entire packing were used for flow simulations. These portions, as shown in Fig. 1(a) and (b) for RSP1 and RSP23, respectively, were discretized with a $128 \times 128 \times 128$ lattice, which corresponded to about 50 lattice points per surface averaged grain diameter. These discretization levels provided grid independent results for low Re and are reasonably sufficient for higher values of Re investigated here, although full investigation of the convergence

FIGURE 2. Three-dimensional flow pattern within a single pore space of the RSP1 packing at varying Re . Stream tubes are used to indicate the flow direction and the width of the tube indicates the variation in divergence of the velocity vector.

at high Re has not been done. The size of domain simulated was not sufficiently large to claim a representative elementary volume. Additional high-resolution simulations will be performed in the future to investigate further the convergence characteristics of the solution as a function of grid discretization, Re , and domain size. However, our present results are sufficiently resolved to provide insights into the behavior of the systems considered.

We simulated flow through the RSP1 and RSP23 packings for Re up to 80. Fig. 2 and Fig. 3, respectively, demonstrate the stream lines through these two packings at various Re . To clearly visualize the flow patterns in three dimensions, we zoomed in on a portion of a flow field within a single pore. Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 show gradual changes of flow pattern from Darcy to non-Darcy regimes. They also clearly show that the pore morphology and topology have an effect on the onset of non-Darcy behavior in that eddies are formed at a lower value of Re for RSP23 than for RSP1.

To evaluate the accuracy of the Forchheimer equation in representing the nonlinear flow behavior, we fitted the non-dimensional pressure drop as a function of Re to Eq. (3).

FIGURE 3. Three-dimensional flow pattern within a single pore space of the RSP23 packing at varying Re .

Fig. 4(a) illustrates that the non-Darcy behavior is captured rather well by the Forchheimer equation. From the slope and intercept of the fitted line, the Forchheimer permeability, κ_f , and the inertial coefficient, β , can be calculated. We obtained $\kappa_f = 4.08 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mm}^2$ for RSP1 and $\kappa_f = 6.86 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mm}^2$ for RSP23. A comparison of these fitted values to the intrinsic permeability κ obtained at zero Re from the solution for Stokes flow with the linear LB equation [17] indicates relative differences of 2.9% for RSP1 and 1.6% for RSP23. These values are in close agreement with the observations of Fourar *et al.* [7], who reported a relative difference of 1.4% for a three-dimensional cell formed from a periodic array of spheres of equal radius.

The values of β were calculated as 90.6 mm^{-1} for RSP1 and 127.5 mm^{-1} for RSP23, indicating that the inertial effect increases with the heterogeneity of the porous media. Moreover, the semi-log scale plot in Fig. 4(b) reveals that inertial effects become important at a smaller Re for the more heterogeneous medium. Further work is needed to derive a correlation model that predicts the inertial coefficient β as a function of porosity and grain-size distribution for sphere packings with log-normal distributions.

Fig. 5 depicts the relative errors between the non-dimensional pressure drop obtained from LB simulation and the prediction from the fitted Forchheimer equation. The Forchheimer equation appears to provide a more accurate approximation at higher Re because

FIGURE 4. Fit of the Forchheimer equation (solid lines) to non-dimensional pressure drop vs. Re data (symbols) obtained from LB simulation with (a) linear scale plot and (b) semi-log scale plot.

it does not take into account the nearly constant drop in non-dimensional pressure when $Re < Re_0$ in the Darcy flow regime. Consequently, when Re is small, the error in the Forchheimer equation is higher for the RSP1 packing than the RSP23 packing which has narrower transition zone between the Darcy and non-Darcy regimes. This trend is consistent with the observations of Fourar *et al.* [7] who found that the Forchheimer equation is more accurate for modeling flow through a three-dimensional cell than a two-dimensional cell with the same porosity and grain diameter because the transition zone between the Darcy and non-Darcy regime is much wider in two dimensions than in three dimensions. The analysis of our simulation results suggests that the form of the Forchheimer equation can be improved by incorporation of a critical Reynolds number Re_0 that better describes the onset of the transition region to the non-Darcy regime. Further simulations are needed to advance such an equation, but microscale simulations of the sort used in this work make such an advancement possible.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we used a multiple-relaxation-time lattice Boltzmann method to simulate single-phase flow over a wide range of Reynolds numbers through two sphere packings with different porosities and grain-size distributions. Three-dimensional flow patterns illustrate the formation of eddies when inertial forces cannot be neglected compared to viscous forces. The formation of eddies at smaller values of Re for the more heterogeneous packing indicates that the pore morphology and topology have an important effect on the onset of non-Darcy behavior. Quantitative study of our simulation data compared to the Forchheimer equation further shows that inertial effects are more significant, and also become important at smaller Re , as the heterogeneity of the medium increases.

The Forchheimer equation is a common approximation for modeling non-Darcy flow at high Re . The transition from the Darcy to the non-Darcy flow regime occurs over a smaller range of values of Re for a more heterogeneous medium. The Forchheimer equation is more accurate when this transition region is small. Based on the calculations and analysis

FIGURE 5. Relative errors between simulation data of non-dimensional pressure drop and those calculated from the fitted Forchheimer equation.

presented, we believe that an improvement to the Forchheimer equation may be possible if the flow transition region is more accurately represented. Such an improved equation could be based upon additional simulations of the sort performed in this work and an analysis that identifies a critical Reynolds number Re_0 where this transition begins. The identification of a new model form and the dependence of the parameters in such a model on measures of the morphology and topology of the pore space will require significant additional simulation.

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